

A Risk-Based Approach to Inservice Inspection

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One approach to scheduling inservice inspection (ISI) of hazardous facilities such as nuclear power and chemical processing plants is to relate ISI reliability and frequency to risk. This approach is based on the fundamental assumption that the purpose of ISI is to detect and correct a degraded condition which, until it is corrected, leads to an increase in risk. The ISI strategy for a set of components is said to be balanced if the increased risk is constant over all components. For a balanced strategy, the product of inspection frequency and detection probability is proportional to the increase in component failure rate which can be detected and corrected by ISI. This result implies a tradeoff between inspection frequency and detection probability.

The purpose of this paper is to relate inservice inspection (ISI) reliability and frequency directly to risk so as to balance the risk associated with ISI over a set of components. This approach is based on the fundamental assumption that the purpose of ISI is to detect and correct a degraded condition, which, until it is corrected, leads to an increase in risk. The increased risk is a function of the consequences of failure and the time to detect the degraded condition. The ISI strategy for a set of components is said to be risk balanced (or simply, balanced) if the increased risk is constant over the set of components.

The starting point for this approach is the notion of baseline failure probability, denoted by P_o . For any component C , failure probability per unit time (usually, per year) is denoted by P . The operational definition of P_o is that no decrease in P is possible if $P < P_o$ while a decrease to $P = P_o$ is possible if $P > P_o$. In practice, P_o is usually equal to the failure probability of the component if it is not degraded below its design capability. However, if the design failure probability is P' , but ISI is not able to detect or correct a failure probability unless it is larger than some $P_o' > P'$, then the baseline failure probability should be set equal to P_o' . From this fundamental assumption, it follows that ISI serves no purpose unless $P > P_o$.

To derive the basic balancing equation, assume that the failure probability of a component C subject to ISI increases from $P = P_o$ to $P = P_o + \Delta P$ immediately following an inspection and remains at this level until detected and corrected, where $\Delta P > 0$ is a constant. Define:

\overline{T}_D = expected time to detect ΔP using ISI techniques

L = consequence due to failure of C

$\overline{\Delta R}$ = expected incremental integrated risk until detection and correction

Then

$$\overline{\Delta R} = \overline{T}_D \cdot \Delta P \cdot L \quad (1)$$

The expected time \overline{T}_D to detect ΔP is, in general, a function of ΔP because the probability of detecting ΔP during any ISI depends on ΔP .

The use of $\overline{\Delta R}$ to measure the effect of an undetected increase in failure probability is motivated by consideration of the expected consequence due to failure of C . If the failure probability per unit time of C is P and persists for a period \overline{T}_D , the probability that C fails during \overline{T}_D is $\overline{T}_D \cdot P$, provided that $\overline{T}_D \cdot P$ is small. [Strictly speaking, $\overline{T}_D \cdot P$ is only an approximation to the failure probability, and the accuracy of this approximation improves as $\overline{T}_D \cdot P$ approaches zero. However, for values of $\overline{T}_D \cdot P$ encountered in practice, the approximation is excellent and is used without further qualification.] Thus, the expected consequence \overline{R} due to the possible failure of C over the period \overline{T}_D is

$$\overline{R} = \overline{T}_D \cdot P \cdot L \quad (2)$$

Since P has units of probability per unit time, the product $\overline{T}_D \cdot P$ is dimensionless and, therefore, \overline{R} has the same units as L . We call \overline{R} the expected integrated risk. If $P = P_o$ then $\overline{R}_o = \overline{T}_D \cdot P_o \cdot L$ is the baseline integrated risk until detection. Since P is elevated above P_o by an amount ΔP for an expected time \overline{T}_D , $\overline{\Delta R}$ is the expected increase in the integrated risk during the period that P remains elevated above P_o .

Let C_1, \dots, C_N be a set of components subject to ISI with $\overline{\Delta R}_i = \overline{T}_{Di} \cdot \Delta P_i \cdot L_i$, where $i = 1 \dots N$. The basic balancing equation is determined by the requirement

$$\overline{\Delta R}_i = K, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

where K is a constant. The motivation for Eq. (3) is that the increased risk due to degradation of any component should be the same for all components.

From the definition of $\overline{\Delta R}_i$, Eq. (3) can be written

$$\overline{T}_{Di} = \frac{K}{L_i} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta P_i} \text{ for } i = 1 \dots N. \quad (4)$$

This form of the basic balancing equation relates the expected detection time to ΔP_i . It shows that \overline{T}_{Di} is a decreasing function of ΔP_i and $\overline{T}_{Di} \rightarrow \infty$ as $\Delta P_i \rightarrow 0$. This makes sense since $\Delta P_i = 0$ means that no inspection or detection is necessary.

If inspection is performed at regular intervals, Eq. (4) can be written in terms of the probability of detection. Let

P_{Di} = probability of detecting ΔP in any single inspection

f_i = number of inspections per unit time.

The expected number of inspections to detect ΔP is $1/P_{Di}$. Since there are f_i inspections per unit time, the expected time to detect ΔP is

$$\overline{T}_{Di} = \frac{1}{f_i \cdot P_{Di}} \quad (5)$$

In general, P_{Di} and \overline{T}_{Di} are functions of ΔP_i . Substituting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4) yields another form of the basic balancing equation:

$$f_i \cdot P_{Di} = \frac{L_i}{K} \Delta P_i \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, N$.

Eq. (6) shows that there is a tradeoff between f_i and P_{D_i} . They are inversely related, so that a decrease in the probability of detection can be compensated for by an increase in the frequency of inspection, and vice versa.

Equations (4) and (6) show that the relationships implied by the basic balancing equation depend only on the ratios L_i/K and not on the absolute values of L_i . If K from Eq. (3) is expressed as a fraction of the baseline integrated risk \bar{R}_o , then the required tradeoffs between f_i and P_{D_i} depend only on the ratios L_i/\bar{R}_o .